

MODELING OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF THE CELL WALL MATERIAL IN NANOCLAY-REINFORCED FOAMS

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1 Introduction

Core materials for the use in sandwich structures are required to have good mechanical performance under shear and compressive loadings. It is, however, known that polymeric foams deform primarily through bending of cell walls [1], which significantly reduces their stiffness and strength. One of the strategies to deal with this drawback is to increase the stiffness and strength of the base polymer, from which these foams are made. It can be done, for example, by reinforcing the polymer with nanoclays [2].

A typical production process of a closed-cell nanoclay-reinforced foam consists of two stages. In the first stage, nanoclays are added to the polymer to prepare a nanocomposite. A high level of nanoclay exfoliation is important. The increase of clay surfaces opened to interactions with the polymer can give a better reinforcing effect [2, 3]. In the second stage, the nanocomposite is foamed. During the foaming process, the nanocomposite is stretched. This is expected to influence the original distribution and orientation of nanoclays in the polymer.

Indeed, it was noted in the literature [4] that stretching of nanocomposite films induced pre-orientation of nanoclays along the stretching direction and led to the formation of nanoclays clusters. Properties of cell walls in foams are, however, often assumed to be equal to the properties of the bulk nanocomposite [5], i.e. isotropic. It means that the effects of clay re-orientation and clustering during the foaming are not taken into account in the models [4-6].

In the present work a new model, which is able to predict anisotropic elastic properties of the cell wall material in nanoclay-reinforced foams is introduced.

2 Modeling Approach

The developed model consists of 3 steps as depicted in Fig. 1. It follows stages similar to the production process of nanoclay-reinforced foams. At the 1st

step, a 3D geometrical model is implemented to generate a representative volume element (RVE) of a nanocomposite (nRVE), i.e. polymer filled with nanoclays. At the 2nd step, a certain procedure is applied to transform the nRVE into a RVE of the cell wall material (cwRVE). This transformation mimics extension of the cell walls during the foaming process. This step brings a novelty to the model in comparison with already existing models of nanocomposite foams [4-6], in which the foam cell wall properties are taken equal to the properties of the unfoamed nanocomposite. At the 3rd final step, the inclusion-based homogenization approach is employed to predict elastic constants of the nRVE and cwRVE.

2.1 Step 1. Generation of a nanocomposite RVE

In order to simulate a RVE of a nanocomposite (nRVE), a geometrical sub-model was developed. Its algorithm is depicted in Fig. 2.

A nanoclay platelet (Fig. 3) is assumed to have a shape of the disc with diameter d_p and thickness t_p . Its position in the nRVE is defined by the Cartesian coordinates of its center (x, y, z) and orientation of the normal vector \vec{n} to its surface with three angles (α, β, γ) . Here α, β, γ are angles between the normal vector and the coordinate axes. If densities of the polymer ρ_m and clay platelets ρ_p , their weight fraction c_p and their orientation distribution ϕ in the modeled nanocomposite are known, the developed code generates a set of clay center coordinates in the 3D space and orientation angles of their normal vectors according to the given distribution ϕ .

In some cases the distribution ϕ can be estimated from transmission electron micrographs of the nanocomposite by means of image analysis [4]. Otherwise, clays are assumed to be fully exfoliated, which delivers maximal reinforcing effect to the

nanocomposite. In this case nanoclays are distributed uniformly in the nRVE. The condition of non-intersection is enforced for all the generated platelets.

The software generates the points and the angles until the desired nanoclay volume fraction v_p is reached. The relationship between the nanoclay weight fraction c_p and the volume fraction v_p can be estimated using the formula:

$$v_p = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{1}{c_p} - 1\right) \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_m}}, v_m = 1 - v_p. \quad (1)$$

2.2 Step 2. Stretching of the nanocomposite RVE

In the second sub-model of this work a transformation procedure of the nRVE into a RVE of the cell wall material (cwRVE) was implemented. The transformation is modeled as a linear extension of the nRVE along the X axis with conservation of the nRVE volume, which leads to compression along the Y axis. The Z direction is fixed for the sake of simplicity (Fig. 1).

An algorithm of the sub-model is shown in Fig. 4. A user defines deformation (a stretching ratio) of the nRVE \mathcal{E}_{CW} . Afterwards, coordinates of any point in the nRVE (x, y, z) can be recalculated according to the formulas:

$$x_{tr} = x\mathcal{E}_{CW}^x, y_{tr} = y\mathcal{E}_{CW}^y, z_{tr} = z, \quad (2)$$

where (x_{tr}, y_{tr}, z_{tr}) are new coordinates of the clay centers in the cwRVE. Simplification $\mathcal{E}_{CW}^z = 1$ can be omitted; in general case deformation can be applied in the Z direction as well.

Any vector is defined with coordinates of two points, namely, its origin and its end. Therefore, new orientations of the normal vectors to clay surfaces $(\alpha_{tr}, \beta_{tr}, \gamma_{tr})$ can be obtained using the same equations (2). Later, new vectors \vec{n}_{tr} are normalized in order to have unit length. As a result of the step 2, nanoclays obtain new orientations and positions within the cwRVE. An example of the transformed nRVE can be found in Fig. 5.

Clays were assumed to be non-deformable in this model because they have much higher stiffness in comparison with polymers (up to 55 times higher for polypropylene (PP), for example).

2.3 Step 3. Homogenization of the RVEs

At the last stage, the inclusion-based homogenization approach (the Eshelby solution and the Morin-Tanaka scheme) is employed to predict elastic constants of the nRVE and cwRVE. This sub-model takes into account different orientations of nanoclays obtained in the previous two steps. A full description of this method can be found in [7].

In this method inclusions are treated as ellipsoids. However, clay platelets have a form of the disc. Due to the difference of the shapes between the disc and the ellipsoid, dimensions of the ellipsoidal inclusions are recalculated to obtain a correct volume fraction of clays in the RVE. From the assumption that volumes of the disc and ellipsoid should be equal, semi-axes of the ellipsoid a_i can be calculated (Fig. 6) using the equation:

$$] a_z = 1, \text{ then } a_x = a_y = \sqrt{\frac{3}{16} d_p^2 \frac{t_p}{a_z}}. \quad (3)$$

3 Input parameters

A single nanoclay platelet (Fig. 6) is assumed to have a shape of the disc with diameter d_p of 200 nm and thickness t_p of 1 nm [6].

Mechanical properties of nanoclays cannot be directly measured in experiments. Therefore, they are usually estimated using molecular dynamic simulations. In the previous works [6, 8-11] montmorillonite platelets were considered as an isotropic material with the modulus of elasticity varying from 140 GPa [8] to 178 GPa [11]. On the average, their Young's modulus is taken equal to 170 GPa and the Poisson's ratio is assumed to be 0.23. [6]. In Pyrz [12] nanoclays were found to be orthotropic with elastic constants summarized in Table 1.

In this work montmorillonite platelets were assumed to be transversally isotropic in the plane XY (Fig. 6) with the constants presented in Table 2. The stiffness matrix of clays can be fully defined if 5 independent elastic constants are known, for example, E_x^p , E_z^p , ν_{xy}^p , ν_{xz}^p and G_{yz}^p . The rest of the parameters can be calculated from the symmetry conditions of the stiffness matrix.

Parametric studies were performed in order to estimate influence of the value of the shear modulus G_{yz}^p on the elastic constants of PP nanocomposite reinforced with 2 wt.% of uniformly distributed

nanoclays. The unknown shear modulus G_{yz}^p was assigned different values in the range between 10 and 150 GPa. Afterwards, properties of the nanocomposite were estimated using the Mori-Tanaka approach. It was concluded that the value of G_{yz}^p did not influence predicted Young's moduli of the nanocomposite. They were found to be the same for any value of the shear modulus in the selected range. In further calculations the value of 30 GPa was adapted as the G_{yz}^p shear property of nanoclays.

4 Results

4.1 The effect of the nanoclay concentration

A set of nRVEs containing randomly oriented nanoclays was generated using the sub-model described in section 2.1. It was found that for high weight fractions (more than 1.5 wt.%) nanoclays cannot be placed randomly in the nRVE without intersections due to their high aspect ratio. Therefore, in order to reach experimentally observed values of 3 or 5 wt.%, clays should obtain the same orientation. In Fig.7 a cross-section of the nRVE with 3 wt.% of clays is depicted. It can be seen that platelets tend to align parallel to each other. Another proof of that a preferential orientation is formed in nRVEs with the increment of clay weight fraction can be found in Fig. 8. Orientation tensor T shows that a preferential orientation along the third axis (Z direction) appeared with increase of clay loading.

The diagonal components of the orientation tensor matrix T_{xx} , T_{yy} , T_{zz} takes values between 0 and 1 and give information about the strength of the orientation of the normal vector \vec{n} to the clay surface (Fig. 3). If $T_{xx}=1$ then all the normal vectors are oriented parallel to the X direction, which means that clays lie in the plane of YZ directions (perpendicular to the X direction). If $T_{xx}=0$ then normal vectors are perpendicular to the X direction. Randomly distributed clays lead to diagonal components equal to 1/3. Moreover, the sum of the matrix diagonal is always 1[13].

4.2 The effect of nanoclay clustering

Given that achievement of full exfoliation of clays in nanocomposites is difficult, platelets tend to form groups of the same orientation (clusters), which are always present in the structure of nanocomposites. Effective properties of agglomerates are always

lower than elastic properties of the single clay platelet. Hence, clusters influence the moduli of nanocomposites [3] and have to be taken into account in the model. By the cluster, a stack of single clays of the same orientation \vec{n}_c with a layer of polymer in between is implied here. Schematic of the cluster consisting of 3 platelets is depicted in Fig. 9.

In this work cluster was modeled as an effective particle, which possesses dimensions of the cluster (thickness t_c and diameter d_p) and its homogenized mechanical properties. The size of clusters, including the average number N of silicate layers per a single stack and the average interlayer spacing d_{001} , are assumed to be predefined. Using the Mori-Tanaka homogenization scheme, effective elastic properties of the cluster were calculated. They can be found in Table 3.

In order to estimate the effect of clusters on the Young's modulus, a set of nRVEs containing different concentrations of the clusters was generated (Fig. 10).

It was observed that clustering of nanoclays reduced the Young's modulus of the nanocomposite (Fig. 10a). This result was well expected because stiffer particles were replaced with the softer ones. On the other hand, an interesting result was observed for E_z modulus (Fig. 10b). In the case of 1.5 and 2 wt.% of nanoclays, the Young's modulus for the composite, containing 50% of clusters from the total amount of clays in the RVE, was higher than for the composite reinforced with completely exfoliated platelets. This observation can be explained by the fact that the presence of clusters in the RVE reduces volume occupied by random platelets. Clusters have more freedom to occupy any place and have any orientation inside the RVE. This assumption is proved by the values of the orientation tensor components:

No clusters

$$T_{xx} = 0.054, T_{yy} = 0.187, T_{zz} = 0.759.$$

50% of clusters

$$T_{xx} = 0.088, T_{yy} = 0.196, T_{zz} = 0.716.$$

The higher value of the component T_{zz} is, the more clays and clusters have the normal vector parallel to the Z axis and, consequently, the lower Young's modulus of the composite E_z is.

4.3 The effect of the cluster size

For this study the nRVEs with 2 wt.% of nanoclays were generated. It was also assumed that 70% of the reinforcements formed clusters. As shown in Fig. 11, the increase of the number of clays per stack significantly reduced the Young's moduli of the composite. For example, the modulus E_x of nanoclay-reinforced PP was reduced by 17% when the number of clays in the cluster was increased from 1 (fully exfoliated) to 5. This result confirms previously reported observations that fully exfoliated nanocomposites exhibit better stiffness than the intercalated ones [3].

4.4 The effect of the stretching ratio

This part of the model aimed to mimic deformations, which nanocomposites go through in the foaming process. For the stretching ratio ϵ_{CW} of 2 along the X direction (Fig. 5), values of the components of the orientation tensor change

From

$$T_{xx} = 0.09, T_{yy} = 0.22, T_{zz} = 0.69;$$

To

$$T_{xx} = 0.3, T_{yy} = 0.43, T_{zz} = 0.27.$$

The increase of T_{yy} means that normal vectors of clays (Fig. 3) become oriented along the Y direction (Fig. 5).

In real foams stretching ratios reach higher values. ϵ_{CW} can be roughly estimated from the images of the foam microstructure. For example, analysis of scanning electron micrographs of a nanoclay-reinforced PP foam showed that a foam possessed microstructure with an average cell size (length of the cell wall) of 1148.39 μm and the average cell wall thickness of 26.96 μm . In this case the stretching ratio ϵ_{CW} is equal to 6.5. For the nRVE reinforced with 1 wt.% of nanoclays, the effect of clay re-orientation in the direction of stretching became more pronounced. Components of the orientation tensor have changed

From

$$T_{xx} = 0.19, T_{yy} = 0.28, T_{zz} = 0.53;$$

To

$$T_{xx} = 0.15, T_{yy} = 0.7, T_{zz} = 0.15.$$

Stretching of a RVE leads to the clay re-orientation and consequently to the increase of the cell wall

stiffness in the X and Z directions. Results of the Mori-Tanaka homogenization are given below:

$$\epsilon_{CW} = 2$$

$$E_x = 2.39 \text{ GPa}, E_y = 2.41 \text{ GPa}, E_z = 2.20 \text{ GPa.}$$

$$E_x = 2.41 \text{ GPa}, E_y = 2.25 \text{ GPa}, E_z = 2.51 \text{ GPa.}$$

$$\epsilon_{CW} = 6.5$$

$$E_x = 2.34 \text{ GPa}, E_y = 2.39 \text{ GPa}, E_z = 2.23 \text{ GPa.}$$

$$E_x = 2.43 \text{ GPa}, E_y = 2.28 \text{ GPa}, E_z = 2.54 \text{ GPa.}$$

5 Conclusions

A new model, which predicts anisotropic elastic properties of the cell wall material in nanoclay-reinforced foams was introduced in this work. The developed model consists of 3 steps, which are similar to the stages of the production process of nanoclay-reinforced foams. Namely, they include generation of a nanocomposite, transformation of the nanocomposite into a cell wall material and prediction of their elastic properties.

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Fig. 1. General flow-chart of the model.

Fig. 2. Flow-chart of the sub-model generating nRVEs.

Fig. 3. Single nanoclay in the nRVE.

Fig. 4. Flow-chart of the sub-model performing transformation of the nRVEs into cwRVEs.

Fig. 5. An example of the nRVE transformation. Stretching ratio \mathcal{E}_{CW}^x is equal to 2.

Fig. 6. Representation of a clay platelet in a shape of the ellipsoidal inclusion.

Fig. 7. A cross-section of the nRVE reinforced with 3 wt.% of nanoclays.

Fig. 8. Components of the orientation tensor T versus clay loading.

Fig. 9. Schematic of a cluster.

Fig. 10. Effect of clusters on the relative Young's modulus of the nanocomposite: (a) in the X direction, (b) in the Z direction. Axes notation is mentioned in Fig. 3.

Fig. 11. Influence of number of nanoclays per cluster on the effective properties of the nanocomposite. The RVE contained 2 wt.% of reinforcements and 70% of them were clusters.

Young's modulus [GPa]		Poisson's ratios			
E_x^p	117.3	ν_{xy}^p	0.53	ν_{xz}^p	1.96
E_y^p	210.3	ν_{yx}^p	0.94	ν_{yz}^p	-0.66
E_z^p	48.0	ν_{zx}^p	0.80	ν_{zy}^p	-0.15

Table 1. Elastic properties of nanoclays [12]. Notation of the axes can be found in Fig. 6.

Nanoclay	
Density [6]	2300 kg/m ³
Young's modulus E_x^p [6]	170 GPa
Young's modulus E_z^p [12]	48.0 GPa
Poisson's ratio ν_{xy}^p [12]	0.53
Poisson's ratio ν_{xz}^p [12]	1.96
Shear modulus G_{yz}^p	was set to 30 GPa
PP	
Density [14]	910 kg/m ³
Young's modulus [14]	2 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.42

Table 2. Mechanical properties of nanoclays and PP matrix used in the study.

Cluster	
Number of platelets per stack N	3
Average interlayer spacing between clays d_{001}	1 nm
Young's modulus E_x	102.8 GPa
Young's modulus E_z	9.57 GPa
Poisson's ratio ν_{xy}	0.53
Poisson's ratio ν_{xz}	1.31
Shear modulus G_{yz}	1.7 GPa

Table 3. Elastic properties of the nanoclays cluster.

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